

Figure 1

A

B

C

D

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5 Overview of each design

PMID	Author	Year	Strategy	Transgene	Effector	In_vitro_model	ETratio	Cytotoxicity	In_vivo_model	In_vivo_results
15287953	Rischer M	2004	CAR	14.G2a CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	GD2+: LAN-1, JF; GD2-: A-204, K562;	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	CD19 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	CD19+: Raji, Reh; CD19-: K562, A204	10 : 1		none	none
23295945	Deniger DC	2013	CAR	CD19-CD28 CAR/Sleeping Beauty (SB)11 transposon	γδ T cells	CD19+: EL4-CD19+, NALM-6; CD19-: EL4-CD19-;	10 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with NALM-6 cells	tumor burden reduced
27598655	Du SH	2016	CAR	mRNA of CD19-CD28 CAR	74% CIK, 20% Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Raji, Sup-B15, Reh	10 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with Raji cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			CAR	mRNA of CEA-CD28 CAR	74% CIK, 20% Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Detroit562	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	mRNA of HER2-CD28 CAR	74% CIK, 20% Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	H292	10 : 1		none	none
28818060	Harrer DC	2017	CAR	mRNA of CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	MCSP+: Mel526, A375M, T2.A1; Daudi;	20 : 1		none	none
			CAR	mRNA of CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	MCSP+: Mel526, A375M, T2.A1; Daudi;	20 : 1		none	none
			TCR-T	mRNA of gp100/HLA-A2-specific αβ TCR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Mel526(gp100+), A375M(gp100-), A375M-pulsed with gp100; Daudi;	20 : 1		none	none
			TCR-T	mRNA of gp100/HLA-A2-specific αβ TCR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Mel526(gp100+), A375M(gp100-), A375M-pulsed with gp100; Daudi;	20 : 1		none	none
28341563	Fisher J	2017	CAR	GD2-DAP10 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	LAN-1(GD2+), TC-71(GD2+), SK-N-SH(GD2-)	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	GD2-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	LAN-1(GD2+)	10 : 1		none	none
29310916	Capsomidis A	2018	CAR	GD2-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	LAN-1(GD2+)	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	GD2-CD28 CAR	Vδ1 or Vδ2 T cells	LAN-1(GD2+)	8 : 1		none	none
29402645	Xiao L	2018	CAR	mRNA of EpCAM CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	CAOV3(EpCAM+), HRT-18G(EpCAM+)	10 : 1		none	none
31824502	Polito VA	2019	CAR	GD2-CD28.4-1BB-CAR	γδ T cells	CHLA255	10 : 1		none	none
31506382	Fisher J	2019	CAR	GD2-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	LAN-1	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	CD33-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	MV4-11	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	CD33-DAP10 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	MV4-11	10 : 1		none	none
			CAR	ErbB2-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	not indicated	na		none	none
			CAR	CD19-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	not indicated	na		none	none
32714329	Rozenbaum M	2020	CAR	CD19-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Nalm6	5 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with NALM-6 cells	tumor burden dropped from 40-60% to ~5%
			CAR	CD19-NSCAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Jurkat(CD5+CD19-), Molt-4(CD5+CD19-)	5 : 1		none	none
32671190	Fleischer LC	2020	CAR	CD19-NSCAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	697 cells(CD5-CD19+)	5 : 1		none	none
			CAR	CD19-NSCAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	697 cells(CD5-CD19+)	5 : 1		none	none
32462079	Ang WX	2020	CAR	mRNA of NKG2D-CD8 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	NKG2DL+: HepG2, MCF7, CAOV3, Detroit562; NKG2DL-: A549;	10 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with HCT116-luc or SKOV3-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved

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33520361	Zhai X	2021	CAR	MUC1-Tn-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	Jurkat(MUC1-Tn+), COSMC-Jurkat(MUC1-Tn-); MUC1-Tn high: T47D, HGC-27, KATO III; MUC1-Tn medium: MDA-MB-468; MUC1-Tn low: MDA-MB-231, SUN-1	5 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with HGC-27 cells	tumor burden reduced	
34916256	Makkouk A	2021	CAR	GPC-3-4-1BB CAR and sIL-15	Vδ1 T cells	HepG2(GPC-3 hi), PLC(GPC-3 low), GPC-3-: SKMEL5, HCT116;	7 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with HepG2 cells	tumor burden reduced	
			CAR	GPC-3-4-1BB CAR	Vδ1 T cells	HepG2(GPC-3 hi), PLC(GPC-3 low), GPC-3-: SKMEL5, HCT116;	7 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with HepG2 cells	tumor burden reduced	
35136603	Nishimoto KP	2022	CAR	CD20-4-1BB CAR	Vδ1 T cells	CD20high: Mino; CD20 mid: Raji; CD20 low: WIL-2;	1 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with Raji cells or JVM-2 cells	tumor burden reduced	
35711450	Ferry GM	2022	CAR	B7H3-CD28 CAR	Vδ1 T cells	B7H3-Jurkat; B7H3+: U87, LAN-1	na	:	none	none	
35295709	Ye X	2022	CAR	FRa-CD28-sIL-7-sCCL19 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	FRa high: MCF-7; FRa middle: MDA-231, FRa-: C30;	10 : 1	:		NOD/SCID mice engrafted with MDA-231 cells or MCF-7 cells	tumor burden reduced
			CAR	FRa-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	FRa high: MCF-7; FRa middle: MDA-231, FRa-: C30;	10 : 1	:		NOD/SCID mice engrafted with MDA-231 cells or MCF-7 cells	tumor burden reduced
36162920	Sánchez Martínez D	2022	CAR	CD123-4-1BB CAR	Vδ1 T cells	CD123+: MOLM13, THP-1; CD123-: Jurkat;	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with AML-PDX-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced	
35496793	Parente-Pereira AC	2022	CAR	MUC1/ErbB-CD28-4-1BB CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	BxPC3(MUC1+, ErbB+)	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with BxPC3 cells	tumor burden reduced	
35709135	Zhang X	2022	CAR	mRNA of BCMA-CD8 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	BCMA high: KMS-11, KMS-18,OPM-2, U266; BCMA-: KG-1;	10 : 1	:		NSG mice engrafted with KMS-11-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			CAR	mRNA of BCMA-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	BCMA high: KMS-11, KMS-18,OPM-2, U266; BCMA-: KG-1;	10 : 1	:		none	none
			CAR	mRNA of NKG2D-CD8 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	BCMA high: KMS-11, KMS-18,OPM-2, U266; BCMA-: KG-1;	10 : 1		:	none	none
37078788	Huang SW	2023	CAR	mRNA of HLA-G nanobody(Nb) CAR and PD-L1-CD3 Nb-BiTE	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	HLA-G high/PD-L1 high: MDA-MB-231, H1975	10 : 1	:		NSG mice engrafted with MDA-MB-231 cells or PD-L1-overexpressing A549 cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			CAR	mRNA of HLA-G-4-1BB nanobody(Nb) CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	HLA-G high/PD-L1 high: MDA-MB-231, H1975	10 : 1	:		NSG mice engrafted with MDA-MB-231 cells	not as much as Nb-CAR.BiTE
37387794	Becker SA	2023	CAR	mRNA of CD19 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	697 cells, Nalm6	5 : 1	:		NSG mice engrafted with 697 cells and Nalm6-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			CAR	mRNA of CD22 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	697 cells, Nalm6	5 : 1		:	none	none
			antibody	mRNA of CD19-CD3 sBite	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	697 cells, Nalm6, JVM-2, Mino, Raji	5 : 1	:		NSG mice engrafted with Nalm6-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
37446055	Wang Y	2023	CAR	CEA-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	CEA+: BxPC3(GD2-), MKN45; CEA-: KP-1N, MIA Paca-2	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with Raji-Luc	tumor burden reduced and survival improved	
			CAR	CEA-CD28 CAR and GITRL(ligand of glucocorticoid-induced TNFR-related protein)	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	CEA+: BxPC3(GD2-), MKN45; CEA-: KP-1N, MIA Paca-2	na	:	NOG mice engrafted with BxPC-3 cells	tumor burden reduced	
			CAR	GD2-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	not indicated	na	:	NOG mice engrafted with BxPC-3 cells	tumor burden reduced	
37134157	Frieling JS	2023	CAR	PSCA-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	C4-2B(PSCA+)	na	:	NOG mice engrafted with BxPC-3 cells	tumor burden not reduced	
			CAR	PSCA-CD8CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	C4-2B(PSCA+)	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with C4-2B cells	not indicated	
			CAR	PSCA-CD8CD27 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	C4-2B(PSCA+)	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with C4-2B cells	tumor burden reduced	

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			CAR	PSCA-CD8-4-1BB CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	C4-2B(PSCA+)	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with C4-2B cells	not indicated
37938576	Lee D	2023	CAR	MSLN-CD28 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	OVCAR3-FG, OVCAR8-FG, SKOV3-FG	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with C4-2B cells	not indicated
			CAR	MSLN-CD28-IL-15 CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	OVCAR3-FG, OVCAR8-FG, SKOV3-FG	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with OVCAR3-FG or OVCAR8 cells	2/5 mice survived 180d in OVCAR3-FG model; tumor burden reduced in OVCAR8 model;
37770968	Wang Y	2023	CAR	B7H3-CD8-CD28-4-1BB CAR	Vγ9Vδ2 T cells	patient-derived tumor cell clusters(PTCs);	1 : 1	:	NSG mice engrafted with OVCAR3-FG or OVCAR8 cells	5/5 mice survived 180d in OVCAR3-FG model; superior control of tumor in OVCAR8 model;
16540688	van der Veken LT	2006	TCR-T	HA-2 αβ TCR, CD4α, CD8αβ	γδ-(αβ) T cells	HA-2 peptide-pulsed EBV-LCL, primary leukemic cell(AML/CML)	10 : 1	:	NSG mice engrafted with U-87MG-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			TCR-T	DBY αβ TCR, CD4α, CD8αβ	γδ-(αβ) T cells	DBY peptide-pulsed EBV-LCL	10 : 1	:	none	none
			TCR-T	CMV-pp65 αβ TCR, CD4α, CD8αβ	γδ-(αβ) T cells	CMV peptide-pulsed EBV-LCL	10 : 1	:	none	none
19242528	Hiasa A	2009	TCR-T	MAGE-A4(HLA-A*2402) αβ TCR, CD8αβ	γδ-(αβ) T cells	MAGE-A4+/A*2402+: 11-18, SK-MEL-128; MAGE-A4+/A*2402-: QG56; T2-A*2402+/MAGE-A4+;	10 : 1	:	none	none
21566093	Marcu-Malina V	2011	TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR(clone G115)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi, K562, KCL22, NB4, BV173, U266; solid tumors: Saos-2, SW480, MZ1851RC, MDA-MB231, SCC-9, FaDu, A231, RPMI2650, Cal27, HNT08;	10 : 1	:	none	none
21909128	Zhao H	2012	TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR with ovarian epithelial carcinoma(OEC) TIL-derived CDR3δ region	αβ-(γδ) T cells	HeLa, HO8910, SKOV3	10 : 1	:	RAG-2/γc neg Balb/c mice engrafted with Daudi-Luc	inhibit tumor with combining pamidronate
23018643	Gründer C	2012	TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR(clone 5)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	Athymic BALB/c nu/nu mice engrafted with SKOV3 cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR(clone 3)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	none	none
			TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR(clone G115)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi; RPMI-8226/s, OPM2, L363, Saos2, MZ1851RC, SCC9, MDA-MB231, SW480	10 : 1	:	none	none
			TCR-T	Vγ9(clone G115)Vδ2(clone5) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi; RPMI-8226/s, OPM2, L363, Saos2, MZ1851RC, SCC9, MDA-MB231, SW480	10 : 1	:	RAG-2/γc neg Balb/c mice engrafted with Daudi-Luc	tumor burden reduced
			TCR-T	Vγ9(clone G115)Vδ2(clone3) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	RAG-2/γc neg Balb/c mice engrafted with Daudi-Luc	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
			TCR-T	Vγ9(clone5)Vδ2(clone G115) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	none	none
			TCR-T	Vγ9(clone3)Vδ2(clone G115) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	none	none
26121617	Shimizu K	2015	TCR-T	mRNA of Va24Vβ11 NKTCR	Vγ9Vδ2-(αβ) T cells	CD1d-HEK293 treated by zoledronate or α-GalCer	10 : 1	:	none	none
25991821	Straetemans T	2015	TCR-T	Vγ9(clone G115)-T2A-Vδ2(clone5) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi, OPM2, RPMI	10 : 1	:	none	none
27463149	He K	2016	TCR-T	Vγ4Vδ1 TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	HepG2, BGC-803, K562, Raji	10 : 1	:	RAG-2/γc neg Balb/c mice engrafted with Daudi-Luc or OPM2-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
28259946	Tao C	2017	TCR-T	αβ TCR Ig constant region exchanged by Vγ9Vδ2 TCR Ig constant region	PBMC	HLA-A2+: HepG2, Huh-1;HLA-A2-: BEL-7402;	10 : 1	:	Athymic BALB/c nu/nu mice engrafted with HepG2 cells	tumor burden reduced
29122757	Legut M	2018	TCR-T	Vγ9Vδ2 TCR(clone γδ20)	β chain-knockout T cells	B-LCL	10 : 1	:	none	none

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30552102	Benveniste PM	2018	TCR-T	Vδ1 paired with Vy8 or Vy4 TCR (clone 5F3 or 3C2 or 1A6[hybrid])	cord blood-derived αβ-(γδ) T cells	MART-1 pulsed T2	6 : 1		none	none	
29899740	Straetemans T	2018	TCR-T	Vy9(clone 5)-T2A-Vδ2(clone5) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi	na	:	none	none	
30479831	Xu Y	2018	TCR-T	ET190L1 Fab and C-terminal signaling domain of γδTCR, ET190L1-CD28 costimulatory molecule	αβ-(Ab-γδ) T cells	Raji, JeKo-2, Daudi, CA46, K562-CD19, IM9, NALM6, MC/CAR	2 : 1		none	none	
30871629	Johanna I	2019	TCR-T	Vy9(clone 5)-T2A-Vδ2(clone5) TCR	αβ-(γδ) T cells	Daudi, primary human acute myeloid leukemia(AML) blast	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with primary human AML cells	tumor burden reduced	
31585951	Kierkels	2019	TCR-T	Vy5Vδ1 TCR(clone FE11)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	SW480, COS-7, K562, Daudi	na	:	none	none	
32019779	Janssen A	2020	TCR-T	Vy4Vδ5(C132), Vy8Vδ5(B23)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	18 solid tumor cell lines, 3 hematologic tumor cell lines	na	:	none	none	
				TCR-T	Vy4Vδ5(C132), Vy8Vδ5(B23)	NKT-(γδ) cells	K562, HeLa, HEK293T, U937 (w/o EPCR)	na	:	none	none
				TCR-T	Vy4Vδ5(C132), Vy8Vδ5(B23)	γδ-(γδ) T cells	K562, HeLa, HEK293T, U937 (w/o EPCR)	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with K562-Luc(HLA-A*24:02)	improved survival
32022317	Johanna I	2020	TCR-T	Vy5Vδ1 TCR(clone FE11)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	none	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with K562-Luc(HLA-A*24:02)	persistent in tumor-bearing mice	
32780528	Ichiki Y	2020	TCR-T	KK-LC-1(HLA-B15) αβ TCR and CD8	γδ-(αβ) T cells	F1121EBV-B pulsed with KK-LC-1, F1121L	10 : 1		NOD/SCID mice engrafted with B901L-HLA-B15 cells	tumor burden reduced in starting treatment after 1w of tumor injection not by 2w	
34575700	Strijker JGM	2021	TCR-T	Vy9Vδ2 TCR (clone5)	αβ-(γδ) T cells	neuroblastoma organoids	na	:	none	none	
34759930	Johanna I	2021	TCR-T	Vy5Vδ1 TCR(clone FE11) and CD8α or CD8αβ	αβ-(γδ) T cells	SW480, EBV-LCL, K562	na	:	NSG mice engrafted with K562-Luc(HLA-A*24:02)	TEG011_CD8α had improved tumor control than TEG011	
35776199	He P	2023	TCR-T	ET190L1-γδTCR and ET190L1-CD28 costimulatory molecule	αβ-(Ab-γδ) T cells	not applicable	na	:	not applicable	not applicable	
37349298	Chen Z	2023	TCR-T	PD-L1 scFV-TRDC or PD-L1 scFV-TRGC with TRAC ribonucleoprotein	αβ-(Ab-γδ) T cells	PD-L1 low: A549, medium: SK-MEL-5, high: MDA-MB-231	5 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with A549 or SK-MEL-5 or MDA-MB-231 cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved, scFv-TRGC had superior efficacy	
				TCR-T	CD19 scFV-TRDC or CD19 scFV-TRGC with TRAC ribonucleoprotein	αβ-(Ab-γδ) T cells	K562, K562-CD19, NALM-6(CD19+)	3 : 1		none	none
36681817	Li C	2023	TCR-T	ET190L1 Fab and C-terminal signaling domain of γδTCR, ET190L1-CD28 costimulatory molecule	αβ-(Ab-γδ) T cells	Raji, Nalm-6(E:T=2:1)	2 : 1		none	none	
18782650	Wang Z	2008	antibody	TRDV2 CDR3δ from γδ TILs to Ig heavy chain(OT3); OT3 chemically conjugated with diphtheria toxin(DT)	monocytes	SKOV3 OEC cells	4 : 1		athymic nude mice intracranial injected with human glioma xenolines	concomitant TMZ and modified-γδ T cells treatment improved survival	
23920126	Zheng J	2013	antibody	ectodomain of Vy9Vδ2 TCR(TCRy9δ2(OT3)-Fc), Vδ2 homodimer(TCRVδ2(OT3)-Fc) or heavy chain of Vy9Vδ2(TCRVδ2(OT3)H/Vy9LΔ)	PBMC	ES-2, SKOV3, Raji	80 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with OVCAR8-Luc	tumor burden reduced and survival improved	
24448235	Oberg HH	2014	antibody	Her2-CD3	Vy9Vδ2 T cells	PancTu-I, Colo357, Panc89	12.5 : 1		none	none	
				(Her2)2-Vy9(clone 7A5)	Vy9Vδ2 T cells	PancTu-I, Colo357, Panc89	na	:	nude mice engrafted with Cal-27; nude mice or C3H mice engrafted with SCC-VII;	tumor burden reduced in nude Cal-27 model and C3H SCC-VII model	
25979810	Oberg HH	2015	antibody	(Her2)2-Vy9(clone 7A5)	Vy9Vδ2 T cells	PancTu-I, Colo357	na	:	nude mice engrafted with SKOV3/HepG2/Hela/HR8348	tumor burden under control in Hela model by OT3-DT	

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27825135	Schiller CB	2016	antibody	CD19-CD16-CD19	$\gamma\delta$ T cells	MCF7-CD19	10 : 1		nude mice engrafted with SKOV3 or ES-2	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
28708284	Peipp M	2017	antibody	CD20 scFV-MICA or CD20 scFV-ULBP2	V δ 1 or V δ 2 T cells	Raji(CD20+),JNA-6(CD20-), Ramos, Daudi and primary CLL;	100 : 1		none	none
29296532	de Bruin RCG	2017	antibody	V γ 9V δ 2 TCR VHH (nanobody) 6H4-5 amino acid linker(5GS)-EGFR VHH 7D12	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	EGFR+: A431, SW480, HT-29, primary colon cancer; EGFR-: JY;	1 : 1		SCID-Beige mice engrafted with PancTu-1 or Panc89	(Her2)2-V γ 9: tumor burden reduced
29725336	Oberg HH	2018	antibody	(Her2)2-CD16	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	PancTu-1, MCF-7, OC11	25 : 1		none	none
32588076	Guo Q	2020	antibody	EpCAM-CD3	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	MDA-MB-231(EpCAM+), SH-SY5Y(EpCAM-)	5 : 1		none	none
31833593	Oberg HH	2020	antibody	(Her2)2-V γ 9(clone 7A5)	PBMC or TIL or TAL(tumor-ascites lymphocytes)	primary ovarian cancer cells	na		none	none
33177109	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	CD40 VHH V19(or V12, V15)-Gly4-Ser linker-V δ 2 TCR VHH 5C8	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	CII, MM.1s, primary CLL	1 : 1or2		BRGS mice engrafted with SW480	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
33526858	Ganesan R	2021	antibody	CD123-V γ 9(clone 7A5)	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	Kasumi-3, MOLM-13, KG-1	1 : 1		none	none
33451981	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	CD1d VHH 1D7-Gly4Ser linker-V δ 2 TCR VHH 5C8	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	Jeko-1, MM.1s(wt vs CD1d), primary CLL	1 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with Raji cells or NALM-6 or primary B-ALL(CHP105R1)	tumor burden reduced
34815357	van Diest E	2021	antibody	V γ 9V δ 2 TCR ectodomain scFV(CL5)-(G4S)3 linker-CD3 scFV(OKT3)	T cells	SCC9, RPMI 8226	na		nude mice engrafted with MDA-MB-231	together with anti-Tim3, tumor burden reduced and survival improved
34040604	Yang R	2021	antibody	PD-L1 Fab-CD3 scFV(clone 2A5)	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	H358, A549, H1299, H1975	1 : 1		none	none
36096643	Lai AY	2022	antibody	BTN2A1/BTN3A1 ectodomain-Fc-CD19 scFV	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	Daudi, Raji, K562-CD19	1 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with MM.1s cell	improved survival
36868236	Lameris R	2023	antibody	CD1d VHH 1D12-Gly4Ser linker-V δ 2 TCR VHH 5C8	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells and type 1 NKT cells	MOLM-13, NOMO-1, CCRF-CEM and primary tumors	1 : 1		NOD SCID mice engrafted with KG-1	tumor burden reduced
36685546	van Diest E	2023	antibody	V γ 9V δ 2 TCR ectodomain scFV(CL5/A)8)-CD3 scFV(OKT3)	T cells	HL60-Luc, RPMI 8226-Luc, SCC9-Luc	5 : 1		none	none
23326319	Lamb LS Jr	2013	gene modification	P140KMGMT (O(6)-methylguanine methyltransferase (MGMT))	$\gamma\delta$ T cells	TMZ-resistant: SNB-19, U373, U87;	10 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with RPMI 8226	tumor burden reduced
34702850	Lamb LS	2021	gene modification	P140KMGMT	$\gamma\delta$ T cells	TMZ-resistant: JX12T; mesenchymal subtypes: JX22T, JX59T	10 : 1		NPG mice engrafted with H1975 cells	tumor burden reduced
37857598	Wang Y	2023	gene modification	humanized PD-1 antibody	$\gamma\delta$ T cells	MDA-MB-231, NCI-H520, BGC-803, A549, HepG2, OVCAR8	10 : 1		none	none
32368439	Wang Y	2018	vaccine	not applicable	$\gamma\delta$ T cell fused with mitomycin C(MMC)-pretreated Saos-2	Saos-2	20 : 1		NSG mice engrafted with MOLM-13, or MM.1s.CD1d cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
30594069	Li L	2019	extracellular vesicles (gdTDEs)	miR-138	miR-138-rich $\gamma\delta$ T cell-derived extracellular vesicles ($\gamma\delta$ TDEs)	Cal-27, SCC-VII	10 : 1		SCID-Beige mice engrafted with Raji-Luc cells	tumor burden reduced and survival improved
37835538	Li HK	2023	antibody-cell conjugation	no transfection; NHS-DNA conjugates: rituximab(anti-CD20 antibody)-DNA linker-2, V δ 2 T cells-DNA linker 1	V γ 9V δ 2 T cells	CD20+: Daudi, Raji; CD20-: K562	10 : 1		none	none